

1 **The immunoglobulin heavy locus is activated in lymph node metastasis in human breast cancer.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer (1); metastasis to the lymph nodes in breast cancer is
7 dangerous, relatively common, and in one study ranged from 10-60% based on molecular subtype (2-4).
8 We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be comprehensively
9 and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data (5). We pioneered understanding of metastasis to
10 the lymph nodes as an intermediate biological and anatomical counterpart to the CNS metastasis in
11 humans (6-12). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (13, 14) to measure total transcription in
12 the lymph node metastases and primary tumors of humans with breast cancer for discovery and insight
13 into clonal evolution through disease progression. We describe here activation of the immunoglobulin
14 heavy locus in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes to study the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer.

Results

Figure 1: IGH is differentially expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

$n=18$ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

$n=16$ lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
215118_s_at	9.23E-05	-4.4265388	1.38526	-1.32574227	IGH	110/22277	99.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer (13), we discovered differential expression of the immunoglobulin heavy locus, encoded by *IGH* in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of IGH changed more than 99% of the human lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of IGH messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of IGH during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

II. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer..

$n=36$ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

$n=36$ lymph node metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
215118_s_at	2.75E-04	-3.8242	0.30873	-1.0919144	IGH	135/22277	99.4

Through measurement of total transcription in the lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer as compared to primary tumors of the breast, we validated differential expression of IGH in metastasis to the lymph node in breast cancer (**Chart 2**) (14). The expression of IGH here changed more than 99% of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of IGH messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of IGH during disease progression and dissemination in humans with breast cancer.

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Thus, differential and increased expression of IGH defines the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

We described here activation of the immunoglobulin heavy chain locus in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer. The data indicate that the B-cell program is activated during disease progression or that IG rearrangement events are associated with metastasis and disease progression.

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Methods

We utilized GSE44408 (13) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE57968 [14] for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.